

Abertay University

MBA - Master of Business Administration

**The Role of Maritime Finance in the Shipping
Industry: Supporting
Global Trade and Economy**

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Table of Figures

Figure 1 Graph for Frequency of Most Common Words	23
Figure 2 Thematic Distribution in Literature and Interviews	24

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. INTRODUCTION	9
1.1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY.....	9
1.2. NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY	11
1.3. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM/RESEARCH QUESTION	13
1.4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY	13
1.5. SCOPE OF THE STUDY.....	14
1.6. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY	15
1.7. ORGANIZATION OF THE REPORT.....	15
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	15
2.1. Literature Search Strategy	16
2.2. Theoretical Framework.....	16
2.3. Economic Impact of Maritime Growth and Port Investments	16
2.4. Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) and Financial	17
Benefits	
2.5. Economic Influences on Greek Maritime Finance	17
2.6. Capital Structure Decisions in Greek Shipping	17
2.7. Policy and the Blue Economy	18
2.8. Blockchain for Transparency and Efficiency	18
2.9. Corporate Governance and Financial Performance.....	18

2.10.	Macroeconomic Factors and Seaborne Trade	19
2.11.	Regulatory Compliance	19
2.12.	Digital Transformation and Blockchain Challenges	19
2.13.	Research Gap	20
3.	RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	20
3.1.	Objectives	20
3.2.	Hypothesis	20
3.3.	Research Design	21
3.4.	Sources of Data.....	21
3.5.	Primary and Secondary data	21
3.6.	Population	21
3.7.	Sample Design	21
3.8.	Sampling method.....	22
3.9.	Method of data collection	22
3.10.	Drafting a questionnaire	22
3.11.	Pilot survey (Reliability and Validity of the instrument) ...	22
3.12.	Data analysis techniques.....	23
4.	FINDINGS, ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION	23
4.1.	Thematic Analysis Findings	23
4.2.	Analysis	25
4.3.	Discussion.....	26
5.	CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS	27
5.1.	Conclusion	27
5.2.	Recommendations	28

6.	REFERENCES	29
7.	APPENDICES	36
7.1.	INFORMED CONSENT	36
7.2.	INTERVIEW QUESTIONNAIRE.....	37
7.3.	INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPTS	38
7.4.	R studio code for thematic coding.....	43

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This research explores the importance of maritime finance and its relevance to global trade and economy. The importance of the financial tools and practices for the development and sustainability of the shipping industry is discussed. The study employs a triangulation design whereby secondary analysis is achieved by conducting an exhaustive review of existing literature, and primary analysis is achieved through interviews. The literature review surveys current scholarship and industry reports to comprehend the state-of-art of maritime finance, its difficulties, and its impact on shipping operations, and global trade. It defines major financial techniques like ship finance, lease and insurance and examines the function of the bank and other financial entities in the international shipping industry by supporting vessels buying and owning, vessel operating and managing, and major construction projects of international shipping structure. The primary sources of data collection were interviews with employees of the related industry, such as financial analysts, shipper managers, and governmental and non-governmental policymakers who contributed primary data about the real-world context of maritime finance. Evaluations from these interviews with other employees included factors such as risks, market factors and elements of change in financing due to the emerging consciousness of sustainability within the industry. The research result underlines the specific role of maritime finance in liquidity provision, innovation, and risk management in the shipping industry. Further, the research presents the current problems faced by the industry, including geopolitical risks, environmental laws, and the ongoing call for innovation. Accordingly, the findings suggests how relations between investors and shipping companies might be improved, opportunities for green finance created, and new technologies like blockchain introduced into the processes.

At the end of the study, it contributes to the understanding of maritime finance, its application in the global economy and how it may be sustained into the foreseeable future.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Shipping is a crucial sector charged with transporting goods across continents. It also has a socioeconomic responsibility to enhance economic growth (Haralambides, 2019). Greece has a long-standing sea-borne legacy and owns one of the largest merchant navies, making it a prominent participant in the international shipping industry (Darques, Sidiropoulos and Kalabokidis, 2024). Bulk carriers, oil tankers, and containers have been identified as the key aspects of Greek shipping companies that contribute to sea-borne trade with Asia, Europe, and America (Kapalidis *et al.*, 2022). However, the future of the Greek shipping industry relies on maritime finance, which is a niche financial discipline that involves providing for ship purchases, modernization of fleets and developing ports.

Moreover, maritime finance is challenged by external factors such as volatility in world markets, shifting marine environment laws and political risks. Conventional funding structures as seen from money lenders, for instance, bank loans and mortgages have become barely available because of the credit crunch, hence leading the Schiff companies to look for funds from other structures such as leasing, bonds, and green financing. In the Greek legal context, maritime finance availability influences the ability of the industry to equip itself and modernize for competition (Tzanatos, Georgiadis and Peristeraki, 2020). However, equal importance is the need to ease the capital structure so that Greece could retain its position as a leading shipping nation amidst increased competition and fluctuating markets.

The scope of this research is to assess and analyze the role played by maritime finance in the development and updating of Greek shipping, as well as its potential contribution to trade productivity and economic growth. This

kind of loan, lease, insurance and investment in port equipment will be discussed in this study concerning enhancing maritime trade routes and facilities (Somorowsky and Haasis, 2020). Thus, answering the key research questions the present study intends to contribute to the understanding of how maritime finance can help improve and sustain the Greek shipping industry for the promotion of economic development in leanness.

1.2. NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The Greek-owned shipping industry has been reported to contribute significantly to domestic and international trade, despite the global crisis, which affected the shipping industry the Greek-owned fleets held 21% of the world's deadweight tonnage in 2023 (Glass, 2023). Greek sea transportation companies are renowned international transporters of crude oil, dry and liquid bulk materials, and containers that have greatly boosted the economy (Goulielmos, 2023). However, sustaining such a stance demands recurrent capital expenditures for new marine vessels, development of ports, and betterment of various operations—factors anchored on maritime finance. This research will seek to understand the implications of maritime finance on the Greek shipping industry and the industry's impact on trade performance and the nation's economic development.

Conventional sources of maritime finance have been shipping mortgages, bank financing and syndicated credit. The funding of Greek shipping companies by European banks is revealed (Grammenos, 2010; Syriopoulos, 2022, p. 39). However, the 2008 financial crisis and subsequent economic volatility in Greece limited the availability of loans and compelled the companies to seek more effective financing options (Alexandridis *et al.*, 2018; Notteboom, Pallis and Rodrigue, 2021). Moreover, a rise in leasing, private equity and ABS through which shipping firms have been able to source funds in mature and uncertain markets (Satta *et al.*, 2020).

Recent development indicates that there is an emergence of green financing, a factor we attribute to international environmental policies. Currently, the IMO has laid down stringent emission goals for the years 2030 and 2050 to encourage shipowners to think of green technology and environment-friendly ships (Dong *et al.*, 2022). Stopford (2009) reveals that green financing comprises a suitable credit package for companies whose operations are aligned to sustainable production. The application of these financial models has become inevitable for Greek shipowners in their attempts to sustain their competitiveness in the emerging environment.

Moreover, risk management has a strategic importance in the financial activities of the Greek shipping companies. Sel and Minner (2022) and Kavussanos and Visvikis (2016) have explored how by using financial derivatives like freight forward agreements (FFA) and currency hedging they are managing risk in a volatile market. Such financial sources assist in regulating operating cash flows to maintain order in a context that is normally unpredictable. However, organizations also face numerous regulations that add to the complexity of their environment, which in turn calls for more robust financial frameworks (Adăscăliței, 2022).

Some empirical work proposes maritime finance, trade and economic growth as having a mix of complementarity (Jansson and Shneerson, 1982). Fleet renewal, the construction of new port terminals, and the use of various digital solutions mean lower supply chain costs and higher competitiveness (Clemente *et al.*, 2023). Hence, for Greece, where shipping is one of the most important economic pillars, having capital is a necessity in its bid to maintain its dominance in the world. About these investments, this study will examine the role of maritime finance to enhance the economy's performance.

Further, financial market regulations and geopolitical changes cause restrictions on maritime finance. The European Union has issued major policies determining capital adequacy and finance for sustainable development

that have changed the lending practices among shipping firms (Kavussanos and Visvikis, 2016). According to Wang, Lu and Yin (2021), the economic uncertainty in the global environment as well as changes in the interest rate can either improve or limit the funding opportunities. So, all these challenges make the position of Greek Shipowners more challenging.

Therefore, within this scholarship, the discussions surrounding maritime finance and the evolution of Greek shipping accrue from the understanding of the impact that financial systems have on shipping-related trade and overall economic progress. Thus, this research will employ traditional and innovative financing mechanisms, regulations on maritime financing, and green financing models that will enhance sustainable maritime leadership in Greece.

1.3. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM/RESEARCH QUESTION

The study will address the following key questions in the context of Greece:

1. What are the primary mechanisms through which maritime finance supports the Greek shipping industry?
2. How does the availability of maritime finance influence the efficiency and competitiveness of Greece's trade routes and global shipping operations?
3. What is the relationship between maritime finance and Greece's economic growth, given the country's reliance on maritime trade?
4. How do shifts in global financial markets and regulatory frameworks, including EU and IMO regulations, affect the structure and availability of maritime finance for Greek shipping companies?

1.4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- To outline the key financial elements that support the Greek shipping sector.
- To evaluate how maritime finance influences the efficiency and competitiveness of trade routes in Greece as well as the global shipping operations active in the country.
- To investigate the patterns of correspondence between marine financial systems and the economic development of shipping in Greece.
- To examine the impact of changes in global capital markets and policy on the provision and form of maritime financing to Greek-owned shipping enterprises.

1.5. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This research focuses on investigating the contribution of maritime finance to the growth and sustainability of the Greek shipping sector. It also seeks to analyze the pertinent aspects of different sources of finance, including but not limited to conventional bank financing, leasing, and green financing in addition to other forms of financing, and how those sources enable the purchasing, updating, and maintaining of vessels. Also, the study looks at the impact that these financial constructs have on the level of efficiency and competitiveness of trade, especially considering the case of Greece in the global shipping environment. The research also considers whether the structures of maritime finance available can be affected by regulatory policies such as those established by the European Union and the International Maritime Organization (IMO) emissions targets. This research thus aims to explore the possibilities, and problems which affect maritime finance,

contributing towards, or interacting with, growth in the Greek economy in the shipping sector, to provide answers as to how Greece can maintain its competitive position in this industry.

1.6. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This research design comes with some problems that could affect the analysis of results. Firstly, the companies' secondary data collection from financial institutions and international organizations as well as through shipping reports may contain potential biases or missing some up-to-date information (Baldwin *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, structured interviews are employed to obtain thorough industry practitioners' information. However, convenience sampling to select participants may reduce the generalizability of the study's outcomes (Orsini *et al.*, 2020). It means that the point of view of selected persons may not necessarily reflect the range of views prevailing in the overall Greek shipping community. Thirdly, the quantitative research paradigm, though strong on establishing quantitative relations, could be weak on quality relations features of theories, including cultural and contextual aspects that probably play significant roles in shaping the prospects of the maritime finance industry. Finally, because the maritime finance environment is ever-evolving, particularly due to shifting international economic situations and new rules, there could be certain restrictions on the actual timings of this research. These limitations point towards the need to proceed with caution when interpreting the results, and to future studies that can fill those gaps and offer a wider understanding of the part that maritime finance needs to play in the Greek shipping industry.

1.7. ORGANIZATION OF THE REPORT

The problem statement has been established based on this, the following is a significant literature review of key sources along with its theoretical framework. The research methodology is explicated followed by

the key findings and analysis. Lastly, conclusions are presented in the final chapter based on primary research analysis.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. LITERATURE SEARCH STRATEGY

To find accurate and credible pieces of research that are relevant to the research topic several keywords have been searched. Based on these search queries, various articles have been gathered, and the ten articles that meet the criteria for the research topic are selected for review. Studying financing sustainable maritime business in Greece examines concepts such as green supply chain financial environmentalism, business economics, capital choices, use of technology by blockchain, and legal bounds impacting the business in the Greek market.

2.2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory is a paradigm that allows for the financing of sustainable shipping practices in Greece (Zaharia and Zaharia, 2021). A TBL rules to harmonization of three factors – economic, environmental, and social dimensions, which lead to financial gains for the companies but at the same time consider the ecology of the society and goodwill (Jayashree *et al.*, 2021). Classic shipping finance theory in Greece allows for the promotion of investment into green supply chain, carbon abatement and technological advancement without compromising on returns. By applying TBL, Maritime companies in Greece can satisfy investors and comply with the law on sustainable development.

2.3. ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MARITIME GROWTH AND PORT INVESTMENTS

Fratila (Adam) *and colleagues* (2021) emphasize that financing the maritime transport and port facilities favours economic development throughout the community of the European Union as seen in the case of Greece. Scholars hold that sustainable maritime investments stimulate and create economic stability and thus contribute to the promotion of sustainable growth of long-term investments and therefore, lays down a clear conception of green finance that dovetails with another broad objective of the EU-US partnership on sustainability as a whole.

2.4. GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT (GSCM) AND FINANCIAL BENEFITS

Alexandrou *and colleagues* (2022) determine the financial impact of green supply chain management within the shipping industry, by arguing that proactive GSCM practices result in financial benefits. This result is specifically significant to Greek maritime firms, where ideas about environmental sustainability can serve as a competitive advantage in terms of revenues and organization management as Greece seeks to retain its leadership position in international shipping.

2.5. ECONOMIC INFLUENCES ON GREEK MARITIME FINANCE

Aivazidou and Politis (2021) analyze the forecasts of maritime passenger traffic and provide economic factors that affect the performance of the Maritime industry that is going to assist decision-makers in the maritime finance industry of Greece. In analyzing the traffic trends and their effects on the economy, they afford a paradigm in financial flows, which, if followed,

can determine funding allocations and be supportive of sustainable funding frameworks within the industry.

2.6. CAPITAL STRUCTURE DECISIONS IN GREEK SHIPPING

While comparing the Greek and Korean shipping firms, Yang, Lee and Lim (2022) pointed out that for economic value, the capital structure has considerable influence. They corroborate the significance of sound financial management, indicating the impact of debt-equity decisions on firm stability in the Greek context, especially in Greek maritime enterprises interested in enhancing financial robustness and effective sustainable finance structures.

2.7. POLICY AND THE BLUE ECONOMY

Nikčević and Škurić (2021) describe Montenegro's integration of Blue Economy strategies that predominantly revolve around policy concerning the use of seas and oceanic resources. This view is well applied in Greek maritime finance since policy encouragement of sustainable practices will pay off and foster industry viability. Greek maritime firms can also pursue similar policy templates to attract investment and promote sustainability.

2.8. BLOCKCHAIN FOR TRANSPARENCY AND EFFICIENCY

Papathanasiou, Cole and Murray (2020) discuss how blockchain may be used in the maritime sector with specific reference to Greek shipping. They talk of the benefits arising from the use of blockchain in increasing transparency and operational efficiency implying that it can revolutionize the Greek of shipping finance. Increased transparency and cost reduction of blockchain leads to more efficient financial reporting and transactions, making it useful in Greece's maritime finance.

2.9. CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

Andrikopoulos *and colleagues* (2021) study the governance question in the context of maritime firms, a concretization in which the authors demonstrate that shares of ownership are worthy of attention where and when it comes to influencing financial performance. This calls for good corporate governance mechanisms in the Greek maritime firms bearing in mind that ownership structure determines the firms' future financial performance and values as embraced by the stakeholders on environmental issues.

2.10. MACROECONOMIC FACTORS AND SEABORNE TRADE

According to Michail (2020), international factors affecting seaborne trade can be analysed from a macroeconomic angle, and about Greece's shipping finance. These aspects will permit the Greek shipping operators to predict changes in market conditions, and thus investment will be made to correspond to the trends without compromising on the strategy of sustainability. This is a useful analysis for dealing with the implications of changes in the marketplace for non-cargo shipping businesses.

2.11. REGULATORY COMPLIANCE

As Wang *and colleagues* (2021) explain the carbon emissions regulation of the European Union laws affecting shipping, it is pertinent for the Greek maritime industry to address this concern. Based on the outlook of competitors' strategic intent becoming more enviable and sustainable regulation, there is a need for reforms in financial strategies born out of growth in rainfall equity allocation strategies.

2.12. DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND BLOCKCHAIN CHALLENGES

Kapnissis *and colleagues* (2022) consider the conditions and factors that limit or facilitate the implementation of blockchain in the shipping business. In their opinion, although the implementation of blockchain technology has the potential to enhance transparency as well as reduce costs, issues like the level of technology preparedness and the existence of laws must be dealt with. In this respect, addressing these challenges for the Greek maritime finance industry would mean that it embraces digital transformation ahead of other sectors.

2.13. RESEARCH GAP

The existing literature has a notable shortcoming in the area of the development of integrated financial approaches in support of sustainable maritime activities in Greece, as it does not provide insight into how to reconcile the conflicting economic, environmental and social objectives of the Triple Bottom Line. Some research focuses on issues such as green supply chain management, blockchain technologies, and capital structure. Still, no research or a theoretical framework exists that explains and analyses the relational impact of these on the maritime finance industry in Greece concerning long-term financial performance and sustainability, especially as domestic markets continue to evolve concerning EU regulations and policy frameworks.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. OBJECTIVES

The objective is to evaluate the extent to which maritime finance has influenced the following aspects of the Greek shipping market. The secondary objective is to assess the sustainable financing opinions of experts and to establish financial initiatives that serve to improve the sustainability of the industry in the context of Greek legislation and economy.

3.2. HYPOTHESIS

This research proposes the following hypothesis: sustainable maritime financing improves the economic profitability and the internationalization process of the Greek shipping business. The assumption is that through embracing green finance and technology Greek shipping firms will experience increased operating reliability and better long-term return prospects.

3.3. RESEARCH DESIGN

The study employs a descriptive research design under the positivism paradigm to meet the objective of establishing the level of correlation between maritime finance and the variables (Park, Konge and Artino, 2020; Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021). This design allows for a systematic assessment of how financing practices affect trade performance and sustainability in the Greek maritime industry.

3.4. SOURCES OF DATA

Data for this research was collected from two primary sources: A literature review was conducted to ground the research in existing scholarly work on maritime finance, the sustainability of the shipping industry, and connections between shipping and economic development. Secondly, interviews were conducted with industry members to tailor data collection more closely to the Greek context.

3.5. PRIMARY AND SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data are collected from scientific journals, market research, and government documents analyzing sustainable finance in maritime firms, economic effects, and environmental standards. Primary data is collected through interviews with the employees of the Greek maritime industry.

3.6. POPULATION

The target audience of the study includes ten senior managers and employees from shipping companies that operate in the Greek market, financial experts and analysts, officials from financial institutions and organizations, and the corresponding governmental and non-governmental institutions.

3.7. SAMPLE DESIGN

A purposive sample of 10 experts who have the best understanding of maritime finance and the Greek shipping industry will be recruited. To achieve this, the sample selection in this study is done in a manner that only respondents with adequate knowledge regarding the subjects of this study are included.

3.8. SAMPLING METHOD

In this study, convenience sampling will be used because the participants must have adequate knowledge of the maritime industry, particularly in finance and sustainability standards (Berndt, 2020; Stratton, 2021). In this particular study, this type of sampling means engaging the appropriate people with the particular happenings' knowledge for context-specific data collection.

3.9. METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

Interviews were used to collect data from respondents. The interview questionnaire (see appendix) is structured in such a way that it yields qualitative data on sustainable financing and challenges within the Greek maritime environment.

3.10. DRAFTING A QUESTIONNAIRE

In the questionnaire (see Appendix B), there are open questions related to financial strategies, green supply chains, and regulatory impact on the

industry performance. All questions will be checked and compared to the purposes of the study and research questions.

3.11. PILOT SURVEY (RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY OF THE INSTRUMENT)

The reliability and validity of interviews among the experts are evident since the sample is scrutinized, and all of them over the years have gained experience. Moreover, from an ethical perspective, interviewees have also signed informed consent beforehand (see Appendix A). This implies that the results are valid and reliable.

3.12. DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

The data analysis will be done using thematic coding of developed questions with the help of interview responses qualitative data is compared to the findings from the literature review to apply the method of triangulation. Qualitative data is analyzed descriptively through R Studio (see Appendix C for interview transcripts and Appendix D for R Studio code) because it is the initial step in establishing facts to guide future research on content analysis patterns and relationships. These results are comprehensive to ensure that they provide sufficient details that show how sustainable finance fits into the bigger picture of operation within the Greek maritime industry.

4. FINDINGS, ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

4.1. THEMATIC ANALYSIS FINDINGS

In the analysis of literature and interviews, the following major themes emerge as emerging or emphasized areas: sustainability in finance, economics, governance and management, technology in sustainability and environmental sustainability. The most mentioned theme was sustainable finance, especially in the interview answers, so there is a growing trend to incorporate sustainable

finance strategies. It was common for participants to raise the new modality of sustainable investment and green funding, which was already becoming almost a standard culture of moving away from business as usual and embedding sustainable elements into financial decision-making processes.

Another important issue that was identified in the literature was the economic influence, which underlined the relationship between international financial policies and economic processes as well as their consequences for development. The discussion of governance also highlighted its importance; mention of regulation and policy, the observance of which is crucial to organizational responsibility and openness, was frequent.

Finally, technology and innovation were used frequently in articles, especially in literature sections covering blockchain, transparency, and efficiency to point out that technology is becoming more appreciated for increasing efficiency and mechanism authenticity. Environmental duties were fairly covered in both resources with the current focus being made on cutting back their carbon footprint as well as adopting Green measures to exemplify the sector's environmental consciousness. Thus, the research suggests greater convergence of sustainability, innovation, and governance with financial practices, pointing to a general transformation of the field's paradigms and frameworks. These findings are evident when the frequency of the most common words graph is as follows:

Figure 1 Graph for Frequency of Most Common Words

Moreover, the graph for the frequency of each word used commonly by the interview participants and literature is as follows:

Figure 2 Thematic Distribution in Literature and Interviews

4.2. ANALYSIS

The outcomes derived from the thematic analysis point out a mixture of sustainability and technological innovativeness in both the literature and the interviews collected data. The fact that most of the responses tended to cover so much on sustainable finance proves the changing order of things in the incorporation of the environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors in investment decisions. This is a settled change that is taking over the industry where there has been a convergence of financial strategies and long-term sustainability as opposed to the traditional practices in investing.

The emphasis placed on the economic impact in the literature points out the fact that more and more organizations are focusing not only on achieving sustainability but also it's more extensive financial outlook where discussions concentrate on the stability and growth of such organizations within the sustainable scope. At the same time though, governance is still an

integral component suggesting that issues like regulatory adherence and management practices that are clean and open are very essential in ensuring the survival of any business in the long run.

The emergence of some technological improvements from the literature such as the blockchain, and innovations that enhance transparency as people are now using technology to make their work more efficient and offer better traceability. Even though environmental responsibility was less attended to. However, its presence catches and highlights the issues of climate change and its emissions in the shipping and finance industries. Therefore, these results say that there is a clear emphasis on organizational performance regarding its sustainability over the period supported by technological advancement and justified governance.

4.3. DISCUSSION

Altogether, the primary and secondary conclusions of the thematic analysis may prove helpful in understanding the changes like sustainable finance and its adoption by organizations. The results of the interviews show that organizations are beginning to adopt and integrate sustainable financing strategies. Structure Many participants stressed the move to sustainable investments with cleaner fuels and Green Bonds; such shifts underscore the global appreciation of sustainable economic development. This trend is consistent with the secondary analysis of the collected literature as well as with such major topics as sustainable finance, governance, and economy identified. In both sources, the trend towards governance is to make sure organizations are compliant with regulations and financial management has sustainable responsibility.

An important topic identified was technological innovation, specifically in the use of blockchain technology, demonstrating how technology innovation is being used to support transparency and improve the

sustainable finance system. Although the concept of environmental responsibility surfaced less in the data, the data shows that organizations are waking up to their impact on the environment, and there was a discourse on cutting down CO₂ emissions. The summarisation of these results highlights not only the shared vision of integrating sustainability into financial management across sectors following technological solutions and governance structures but also the need for financial and environmental sustainability.

5. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. CONCLUSION

Ultimately, maritime finance is a key catalyst for the shipping sector, which underpins global trade and sustains economies. The shipping industry, which is at the centre of international trade, depends on a wide range of specialized financial services, including ship financing, leasing, or risk-taking to run efficiently and sustainably. Thanks to maritime financing, shipping companies can take advantage of the escalating demand to construct new fleets, upgrade technology, and comply with regulations all of which come with additional costs and restrictions that also include high fuel prices and stringent environmental controls. Moreover, the implementation of green ship financing and ESG investments, amongst other sustainable finance approaches, demonstrates the industry's willingness to seek profits even in the face of climate change. With globalization on the upward rise, it can be predicted that just like global trade, the involvement of maritime finance and its creativity will expand even more. Also, with the evolution of the maritime financing structure which includes digitalization and other sources of financing, the industry will become more dependable and dynamic. Therefore, this form of financing for shipping and other maritime activities is of great importance to the global economy because it enables the ocean transportation system to perform its essential function of connecting disparate markets for

economic activities and facilitating the movement of goods across countries and continents.

5.2. RECOMMENDATIONS

To strengthen the role of maritime finance for stirring up international trade and the world economy, the below factors should be considered. First of all, at the policy level, enhanced collaboration needs to be constructed between the increasing number of financial institutions, shippers and regulators in order to devise industry-specific financing schemes and promote green initiatives (Meng *et al.*, 2022). The financial institutions must play a key role in the marketing of green financing schemes to steer the shipping companies towards sustainable solutions and innovations, including low-emission vessels and renewable energy solutions towards the achievement of the industry's long-term ecology missions. In addition, attention is given to the implementation of sound risk control measures and practices for instance the effects of geopolitics, market volatility, and even climate change (Iriani *et al.*, 2024). This way, it can be concluded that in order to mitigate these financial risks, better risk assessment models need to be developed by shipping firms and their portfolios re-balanced accordingly. In addition, digitalization offers many promising prospects for improving the effectiveness and increasing the clarity of the financing of the maritime industry. The industry should embrace the use of blockchain and fintech to enhance the efficiency of the transactions and cut expenses, while at the same time providing funding to the players who seem to be less favoured in the market (Ahmad *et al.*, 2021; Alade and Eroglu, 2023). Lastly, the promotion of educational programs on maritime finance in academic institutions will help in training future leaders to adequately respond to the challenges the financial sector is bound to face in the future (Autsadee *et al.*, 2023). These steps will help in the development and sustenance of the shipping industries.

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7. APPENDICES

7.1. INFORMED CONSENT

Study Title: The Impact of Sustainable Maritime Finance on the Greek Shipping Industry

Purpose of the Study

This study aims to understand the role of maritime finance in enhancing sustainability and economic growth within the Greek shipping industry. We are conducting interviews with experts to gather insights on financial strategies, green financing practices, and the challenges within the maritime sector.

Participation Details

As a participant, you will be asked to engage in an interview lasting approximately 20 minutes. Your responses will contribute valuable insights and support the study's objectives to analyze the effects of sustainable financing in the maritime industry. Participation is voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without any repercussions.

Confidentiality

All information provided during the interview will be treated confidentially. Your name and other identifying details will not appear in any report or publication resulting from this study. Data collected will be securely stored, accessible only to the research team, and used solely for academic purposes.

Benefits and Risks

Your participation will aid in understanding sustainable finance's influence in the maritime sector, potentially informing future industry practices and policy recommendations. There are no foreseeable risks involved in participating.

Right to Withdraw

You have the right to withdraw from the study at any point, for any reason, without penalty. If you choose to withdraw, any data collected from you will be destroyed immediately.

Consent

By signing below, you acknowledge that you understand the purpose of this study, your role in it, and the conditions of your participation. You consent to take part in this interview voluntarily.

Participant's Statement

I have read and understood the information above. I consent to participate in this study and agree that the interview data may be used for research purposes under the conditions outlined.

Participant's Name: _____

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: _____

7.2. INTERVIEW QUESTIONNAIRE

1. How has the concept of sustainable financing influenced financial strategies within your organization?
2. What are the biggest challenges your organization faces in implementing sustainable finance practices?

3. In your experience, how does access to sustainable finance affect the competitive positioning of Greek shipping firms in the global market?
4. What role do you believe regulatory frameworks and government policies play in promoting sustainable finance within the Greek maritime industry?
5. How do you perceive the future of sustainable finance in the Greek maritime industry?

7.3. INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPTS

Participant 1

1. Sustainable financing has encouraged us to diversify our funding sources, especially by looking for green bonds and loans. These instruments incentivize us to reduce our emissions and improve environmental practices.
2. One of the major hurdles is the lack of experienced personnel familiar with sustainable finance. It's a new field, so training our team takes time and resources.
3. Access to sustainable finance gives us a competitive edge because clients and partners value our commitment to environmental responsibility. It attracts global shippers with strong ESG commitments.
4. Greek regulations on environmental protection have been useful but could be more robust. Stronger policies would standardize sustainable practices across the sector.
5. I believe sustainable finance will become mainstream as investors demand more green practices. In the future, non-sustainable practices may even limit a company's financial opportunities.

Participant 2

1. We've aligned our finance strategies with sustainable finance standards, reducing emissions and waste. Green financing is now part of our long-term planning.
2. The cost of implementing green technology is significant. It's challenging to balance sustainability with profitability, especially for older vessels.
3. Sustainable finance allows us to position ourselves as a responsible choice, which appeals to European and American clients committed to green practices.
4. The government has supported sustainable finance, but there's inconsistency. Clearer incentives for companies adopting green finance would help accelerate adoption.
5. Sustainable finance will likely define the future of Greek shipping. As more clients prioritize sustainability, only firms committed to it will thrive.

Participant 3

1. Sustainable financing has led us to rethink our asset management and consider lifecycle impacts. We're making decisions that factor in environmental costs over the vessel's lifespan.
2. The main challenge is retrofitting our existing fleet. We need funding to upgrade older ships, which is costly without strong financial backing.
3. Access to sustainable finance strengthens our market reputation, attracting clients who value eco-friendly operations. It's an important factor in our competitive strategy.
4. The regulatory framework is moving in the right direction, but the industry would benefit from stricter standards and better incentives for early adopters.

5. The future is promising, especially as the EU increases its sustainability targets. Greek shipping companies will need to evolve or risk falling behind.

Participant 4

1. We're now seeking investors who value sustainable practices, which has opened doors to new international partnerships focused on green shipping.
2. A big challenge is the lack of local financial products tailored to the maritime sector's needs. Most green financing options are too generic and don't fit our specific requirements.
3. Having access to sustainable finance distinguishes us as a forward-thinking company. It aligns us with leading international firms and clients looking for green solutions.
4. Current policies are a good start, but they could be better enforced. Some companies aren't serious about sustainability, which hurts the industry as a whole.
5. I foresee more partnerships between finance and maritime sectors. Innovations in green finance will be critical to the Greek industry's growth.

Participant 5

1. Sustainable finance has encouraged us to invest in cleaner fuel options and energy-efficient technologies, which also improve our long-term cost structure.
2. Our biggest issue is navigating the complexity of green financing criteria. Each lender has different expectations, making it hard to meet them all.
3. With sustainable finance, we position ourselves as leaders in green shipping, which is appealing to our environmentally conscious clients worldwide.

4. Government policies have helped, but they're reactive rather than proactive. A more forward-thinking approach would support sustainability better.
5. In five years, I expect sustainability to be a prerequisite for financial support. Only those who can prove their green practices will survive.

Participant 6

1. We've adopted sustainable finance by issuing bonds tied to emissions reductions. This has forced us to prioritize environmental targets.
2. Sustainability is costly, and passing these costs onto customers is challenging. Some clients may choose cheaper, non-green competitors.
3. It enhances our reputation, but the challenge is ensuring we have the resources to maintain these standards amid economic fluctuations.
4. Greece has set some beneficial policies, but enforcement is lacking. Stronger oversight would push more firms to comply.
5. Sustainable finance will drive the industry forward, but it's essential for Greece to keep pace with global green finance trends.

Participant 7

1. Sustainable financing has shifted our focus towards long-term gains and reduced environmental impact rather than only short-term profits.
2. The challenge is aligning our practices with international sustainability standards, which are evolving rapidly.
3. Sustainable finance sets us apart from competitors. Clients now prioritize environmental performance, especially European clients.
4. Government policies help, but they're fragmented. Cohesive policies would make sustainable finance easier to adopt on a larger scale.
5. I think sustainable finance will transform the industry, but the pace will depend on regulatory support and industry collaboration.

Participant 8

1. We've become more selective about projects and clients, prioritizing those who align with sustainable financing principles.
2. Accessing sustainable finance is challenging, as it requires high transparency and detailed reporting, which many companies lack.
3. With sustainable finance, we gain a competitive edge, especially with multinational clients that mandate green partnerships.
4. Greek policies promote sustainable finance, but they need to target small-to-medium maritime firms, which struggle with the costs.
5. The future looks promising, but only for firms ready to invest in green technologies and align with global sustainability standards.

Participant 9

1. Sustainable financing has led us to prioritize fuel efficiency and reduce operational costs through sustainability-driven technology investments.
2. High upfront costs for sustainability projects are a significant barrier, especially in times of market uncertainty.
3. Green financing attracts clients and investors who value sustainability, positioning us as a preferred partner in eco-conscious markets.
4. The government's role is supportive, but stronger incentives and lower taxes for green initiatives would accelerate adoption.
5. Sustainability will be the new standard, and I expect green finance to become a core criterion for companies to operate globally.

Participant 10

1. We've integrated sustainable financing by focusing on green bonds to support eco-friendly retrofitting of our older vessels.
2. Finding local financing partners with experience in green finance is challenging. We often look abroad, which complicates processes.
3. Sustainable finance supports our brand image, making us a competitive choice for clients who prioritize environmental accountability.

4. Government policies are a step in the right direction, but their impact is slow. More rapid implementation would benefit the industry.
5. Sustainable finance will define the future, but firms must act quickly to meet new standards as investor expectations grow stricter.

7.4. R STUDIO CODE FOR THEMATIC CODING

```
---  
  
title: "Thematic Coding"  
  
output: html_document  
  
date: "2024-11-08"  
  
---  
  
```${r setup, include=FALSE}  

knitr::opts_chunk$set(echo = TRUE)

Load libraries

library(dplyr)

library(tm)

library(tidytext)

library(tidyr)

library(text) # If installed for summarization tasks

library(stringr)

library(ggplot2)
```

```

'''
Load the text

```{r load-data, eval=TRUE}

# Read in the cleaned analysis datafile using a relative path
# to specify that the data file is in the "AnalysisData" folder
literature_data <- data.frame(

  Section = c("Literature Search Strategy", "Theoretical Framework",
"Economic Impact", "Green Supply Chain",

  "Economic Influences", "Capital Structure", "Policy and Blue
Economy", "Blockchain Transparency",

  "Corporate Governance", "Macroeconomic Factors",
"Regulatory Compliance", "Digital Transformation"),

  Content = c(

    "In order to find accurate and credible pieces of research...",

    "The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory is a paradigm that allows for
the financing...",

    "Fratila (Adam) and colleagues (2021) emphasize that the financing
in the maritime...",

    "Alexandrou and colleagues (2022) determine the financial impact
of green supply chain...",

    "Aivazidou and Politis (2021) analyze the forecasts of maritime
passenger traffic...",

```

"While comparing the Greek and Korean shipping firms...",

"Nikčević and Škurić (2021) describe the Montenegro's integration of Blue Economy...",

"Papathanasiou, Cole and Murray (2020) discuss how blockchain may be used...",

"Andrikopoulos and colleagues (2021) study the governance question...",

"According to Michail (2020), international factors affecting seaborne trade...",

"As Wang and colleagues (2021) explain the carbon emissions regulation...",

"Kapnissis and colleagues (2022) consider the conditions and factors..."

),

stringsAsFactors = FALSE

)

``

Interview data

``{r interview data, eval=TRUE}

interview_data <- data.frame(

```
Participant = c("Participant 1", "Participant 2", "Participant 3",  
"Participant 4",  
"Participant 5", "Participant 6", "Participant 7", "Participant  
8",  
"Participant 9", "Participant 10"),  
Response = c(  
"Sustainable financing has encouraged us to diversify our funding  
sources...",  
"We've aligned our finance strategies with sustainable finance  
standards...",  
"Sustainable financing has led us to rethink our asset  
management...",  
"We're now seeking investors who value sustainable practices...",  
"Sustainable finance has encouraged us to invest in cleaner fuel  
options...",  
"We've adopted sustainable finance by issuing bonds tied to  
emissions reductions...",  
"Sustainable financing has shifted our focus towards long-term  
gains...",  
"We've become more selective about projects and clients...",  
"Sustainable financing has led us to prioritize fuel efficiency...",  
"We've integrated sustainable financing by focusing on green  
bonds..."  
)
```

```

stringsAsFactors = FALSE
)
```

Combine the data

```{r combine data, eval=TRUE}

combined_data <- bind_rows(
  literature_data %>% mutate(Source = "Literature"),
  interview_data %>% mutate(Source = "Interview")
)
```

Tokenize the text

```{r tokenize text, eval=TRUE}

tokens <- combined_data %>%
  unnest_tokens(word, Content) %>%
  anti_join(stop_words) # Remove common stop words

```

Visualize

```

```

```{r vizualize, eval=TRUE}

word_count <- tokens %>%
  count(word, sort = TRUE) %>%
  filter(n > 5) # Adjust this filter as necessary for your analysis

ggplot(word_count, aes(x = reorder(word, n), y = n)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity") +
  coord_flip() +
  labs(title = "Most Common Words in Literature and Interview
Responses", x = "Word", y = "Frequency")

```

Thematic coding

```{r thematic coding, eval=TRUE}

themes <- list(
  "Sustainable Finance" = c("sustainable", "finance", "green",
"investment", "funding"),
  "Economic Impact" = c("economic", "growth", "investment",
"stability"),

```

```

    "Governance" = c("governance", "policy", "regulation",
"compliance"),

    "Technology and Innovation" = c("blockchain", "transparency",
"efficiency", "technology"),

    "Environmental Responsibility" = c("environmental", "carbon",
"emissions", "sustainability")

)

```

Create new data frame

``` {r new data, eval=TRUE}

thematic_data <- combined_data %>%

rowwise() %>%

mutate(

    Sustainable_Finance = sum(str_count(Content,
paste(themes[["Sustainable Finance"]], collapse = "|")),

    Economic_Impact = sum(str_count(Content,
paste(themes[["Economic Impact"]], collapse = "|")),

    Governance = sum(str_count(Content,
paste(themes[["Governance"]], collapse = "|")),

    Technology_Innovation = sum(str_count(Content,
paste(themes[["Technology and Innovation"]], collapse = "|")),

    Environmental_Responsibility = sum(str_count(Content,
paste(themes[["Environmental Responsibility"]], collapse = "|")))

)

```

```

'''
## View thematic frequency

'''{r view thematic, eval=TRUE}

summary_thematic <- thematic_data %>%

  summarise(

    Sustainable_Finance = sum(Sustainable_Finance),

    Economic_Impact = sum(Economic_Impact),

    Governance = sum(Governance),

    Technology_Innovation = sum(Technology_Innovation),

    Environmental_Responsibility =
sum(Environmental_Responsibility)

  )

print(summary_thematic)

'''

## Plotting thematic distribution across sources

'''{r thematic distribution, eval=TRUE}

theme_plot_data <- thematic_data %>%

  pivot_longer(cols =
Sustainable_Finance:Environmental_Responsibility,

    names_to = "Theme",

    values_to = "Count") %>%

```

```
group_by(Source, Theme) %>%  
summarise(Total = sum(Count))  
  
ggplot(theme_plot_data, aes(x = Theme, y = Total, fill = Source)) +  
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "dodge") +  
  labs(title = "Thematic Distribution in Literature and Interview Data",  
x = "Theme", y = "Frequency") +  
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1))  
'''
```